

Wind Powered UAV

Wind powered UAV is a form of UAV that once reaches a high altitude has never to land back, it will generate energy from high speed cross winds in the high atmosphere. The UAV once took off never have to land and will store energy in Electron Batteries. Theoretically the UAV will never have to land back once started flying for refuelling and can carry heavy payloads.

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Overview

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The physical ~~environmental~~ system will influence during their development and formation. This stage will derive information regarding their government ~~shape~~ ~~with~~ technical store and physical space conditions within this...

